

THE EFFECT OF STRESS COPING METHODS ON LIQUID DIET COMPLIANCE OF HAEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS

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Keywords

Chronic renal failure,

Haemodialysis,

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Liquid diet compliance

ABSTRACT

In the study, it was aimed to determine the effect of stress coping levels of haemodialysis patients on their liquid diet compliance. In this descriptive study, while all patients undergoing dialysis in the haemodialysis unit of a university hospital constituted the population of the study, all patients who volunteered to participate in the study between 19 September and 19 October 2023, who could communicate face-to-face and who were conscious constituted the sample of the study, and 95 patients were reached with a margin of error of 0.05 in the 95% confidence interval. According to the data obtained from the study, sociodemographic factors such as gender, marital status, educational status, presence of comorbidity, and employment status significantly affected the coping with stress levels of the patients, and a significant relationship was determined between coping with stress and liquid diet compliance. Accordingly, it was determined that patients with higher levels of coping with stress had higher liquid diet compliance. In the light of all this information, strengthening the coping mechanisms of people diagnosed with a chronic disease such as chronic renal failure (CRF), which affects all areas of life, and increasing their coping with the disease will facilitate their compliance with liquid diets.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic diseases constitute an important problem for public health today. Chronic renal failure (CRF) is one of the important chronic diseases that cause chronic and progressive deterioration in metabolic and endocrine functions of the kidneys. Chronic renal failure (CRF) is an important disease leading to life-threatening organic, mental and psychosocial problems and various complications¹.

In the treatment of chronic renal failure, dialysis is a form of treatment applied until transplantation is performed. Although different treatment options are offered to CRF patients today, haemodialysis is still the most commonly used treatment method in Turkey due to economic and technical possibilities. When we look at the rates of treatment modalities in Turkey, haemodialysis ranks first with 75.7%². Haemodialysis is a method used to remove waste materials and excess fluid from the body. In this process, patients need to comply with a certain fluid intake. Fluid diet is critical to maintain patients' renal function and prevent complications³. Insufficient fluid intake can lead to dehydration, while excessive fluid intake can increase the risk of hypertension and heart failure⁴.

Stress is an important factor affecting the psychological and physical health of haemodialysis patients. The haemodialysis process can create psychological pressure on patients, which can increase stress levels⁵. High stress levels can negatively affect individuals' health behaviours, which can make fluid diet compliance difficult⁶. If the stressors arising due to dialysis treatment can be perceived realistically by the patient, adequate and appropriate situational support is provided, and effective coping mechanisms are available, patients can restructure their lives and establish balance, thus preventing the occurrence of a crisis. However, in the absence of one or more of these stabilising factors, the individual cannot solve the problems and a crisis may occur. Effective coping is important in preventing crisis. In cases where coping is not effective, adaptation problems and mental problems may be observed in patients⁷.

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Patients' methods of coping with stress may affect their compliance with the liquid diet. Stress management techniques may improve the emotional state of patients and this may positively affect their health behaviours⁸. As in the treatment of all diseases, the adaptation process is important in haemodialysis patients. Successful haemodialysis treatment requires compliance with diet, fluid restriction, regular use of medications and regular dialysis follow-up⁷. Haemodialysis patients have problems in fulfilling activities of daily living, diet compliance and fluid restriction due to decreased self-care power and disability⁹. Excess fluid and dietary non-compliance are common problems in haemodialysis patients^{6,10}. The most stressful conditions in dialysis patients are potassium and phosphate-restricted diet and limitation of water and salt intake¹¹. The hypotheses of the study were as follows:

- Socio-demographic characteristics affect stress coping levels of haemodialysis patients.
- Socio-demographic characteristics affect liquid diet compliance of haemodialysis patients.
- Coping with stress levels of haemodialysis patients affect liquid diet compliance' hypotheses.

Stress coping levels of haemodialysis patients have a significant effect on their liquid diet compliance. The application of stress management techniques may help patients to regulate their fluid intake. Therefore, it is of great importance that haemodialysis patients receive psychological support and learn stress coping methods. In the literature, although there are studies investigating the stress coping levels of haemodialysis patients, there are no studies associated with fluid diet compliance. In this sense, it is thought to be a very valuable study in terms of its high original value and widespread effect.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethical Principles

Before starting the research work, the necessary The situation was determined and approvals were obtained. **** Ethics Committee (Approval Date: 17/05/2023; Approval Number: 2023-05/05). In addition, written authorisations have been obtained from organisations that act as operational contexts for this study. With unwavering transparency, I have been able requests communicated, harmonised smoothly. Ethical principles covering 'Confidentiality and Reliability' and

Protection of Privacy', "Respect for Autonomy" and The overarching principle of 'Do No Harm/Benefit'. This one the realisation of these ethical principles has been achieved by enrolment of participants who volunteered to participate, so that preserving their autonomy. As an embodiment of this commitment, the research meticulously adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the Helsinki Declaration of Human Rights throughout the entire trajectory of its implementation.

Type of Research

This study was planned as a descriptive study to determine the relationship between the levels of coping with stress used by haemodialysis patients and their liquid diet compliance. The population of the study consists of all patients hospitalised in **** Hospital Dialysis Service. All patients undergoing haemodialysis in *** Hospital Dialysis Service between 19 September and 19 October 2023 constitute the sample of the study. All patients who agreed to participate in the study, who were conscious and open to communication were included in the study and 95 patients were reached with a margin of error of 0.05 in the 95% confidence interval. Data will be collected by using the socio-demographic form prepared in line with the literature, the Stress Coping Methods Scale and the Scale of Non-compliance with Diet and Fluid Restriction.

Data Collection Tools

Patient Introduction Form

The patient introduction form was prepared based on the literature^{12,13}. It consists of 8 questions including information such as age, gender, marital status, educational status, employment status, presence of an additional chronic disease, and previous hospitalisation status of the patient.

Stress Coping Methods Scale

In the study, the coping scale developed by Moos. and tested for reliability and validity by Ata et al. was used^{14,15}. The original scale consists of two parts as avoidance and approach responses and eight dimensions in total. Since only one part of the scale (approach reactions) and four dimensions (logical analysis, positive appraisal, seeking guidance and support, problem solving) were used in the reliability and validity study, we used it in this form. The scale consisting of 24 statements was graded on a 5 point Likert scale and the response options were scored as 1-Never, 2-Rarely, 3-Sometimes, 4-Mostly, .5-Always. Questions 1-5-9-13-17-21 of

the scale belong to logical analysis; 2-6-10-14-18-22 of the scale belong to positive evaluation; 3-7-11-15-19-23 of the scale belong to seeking support; 4-8-12-16-20-24 of the scale belong to problem solving sub-dimensions. Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was calculated to determine the reliability of the scale by İpek et al. Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of the scale was found to be 0,93.

Dialysis Diet and Fluid Restriction Non-Compliance Scale (DDSS)

This scale was developed by Vlaminck et al. to assess the non-compliance with diet and fluid restriction in individuals receiving HD treatment ¹⁶. The validity and reliability of this scale in Turkey was performed by Kara and Cronbach's alpha coefficient was found to be 0.70 ¹⁷. There are four questions in the scale. The first and second questions ask about the frequency and degree of non-compliance with the patient's diet, and the third and fourth questions ask about the frequency and degree of non-compliance with fluid restriction. To assess the frequency of dietary and fluid restriction non-compliance, the number of days with non-compliant behaviour in the last 14 days is asked. The degree of non-compliance with dietary and fluid restriction is determined by Likert-type scoring between 0-4 (No non-compliance=0 points, mild=1 point, moderate=2 points, severe=3 points and very severe=4 points). The higher the scores obtained in the scale, the higher the incompatibility of individuals ¹⁷. In this study, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of internal structure consistency was found to be 0.72.

Data Analysis

SPSS 22.0 package programme was used for statistical evaluation of the data. The normality of the data was examined by Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, number, percentage and mean \pm standard deviation for continuous variables were used to examine the descriptive characteristics of the patients. If the data met the parametric conditions, they were analysed with independent sample t test for two independent groups and F test (ANOVA) for more than two groups. The error level was taken as 0.05.

For comparisons involving two independent groups, the Independent Samples t-test was used when normality and sample size assumptions were met; otherwise, the Mann-Whitney U test was applied. For comparisons involving more than two groups, ANOVA was used under parametric assumptions and Kruskal-Wallis H test was used when

assumptions were not met or group sizes were small (e.g., $n < 30$). Chi-square test was used for examining the relationships between categorical variables (e.g., gender, marital status) and categorical groupings of stress coping levels. To evaluate the relationship between continuous variables, Pearson correlation was used when both variables showed normal distribution; otherwise, Spearman's rho was applied. The level of statistical significance was accepted as $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the distribution of some socio-demographic characteristics of the participants. Accordingly, the majority of the patients (71.6%) were male and the majority (70.5%) were married. University graduates constituted the least number of patients (10.5%) and more than half of the patients (50.6%) were retired. It was determined that the patients had comorbidities (61.1%) and had been hospitalised before (81.1%) and most of them (81.1%) were on dialysis three times a week.

Table 2 shows the comparison of the Stress Coping Methods Scale with some socio-demographic characteristics. Accordingly, male patients coped with stress more than female patients and the result was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). In addition, when analysed with sub-dimensions, it was seen that all dimensions except the sub-dimension of seeking support had a significant relationship with gender. While the positive evaluation sub-dimension was higher in women, the logical analysis and problem solving dimensions were higher in men and statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The marital status of the participants was also found to be significantly effective on their coping with stress. While the coping with stress of the married participants was higher, problem solving and support seeking sub-dimensions were also higher in the married participants. This difference is also statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). When the educational status and coping methods with stress are analysed, it is seen that the coping with stress of university graduates is lower and statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). In all sub-dimensions of coping with stress, it was determined that the coping of university graduates was lower and the result was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This situation can be interpreted as the coping with stress decreases as the awareness increases. The presence of comorbidity and previous hospitalisation experience were also significantly effective on coping with stress ($p < 0.05$). While coping with stress was significantly higher in people with comorbidities,

copied with stress was similarly higher in people who had not been hospitalised before ($p < 0.05$). It was determined that both previous hospitalisation and the presence of comorbidity did not create a significant difference in the problem solving sub-dimension of coping with stress ($p > 0.05$). The fact that the participants were actively working significantly increased their coping with stress ($p < 0.05$), while the coping of patients who were housewives was lower.

Table 1. Distribution of Participants According to Some Socio-demographic Characteristics (n=95)

Socio-demographic Characteristics (n=95)		n	%
Gender	Female	27	28.4
	Male	68	71.6
Marital Status	Married	67	70.5
	Single	28	29.5
Education Status	Primary Education	19	20.0
	Middle School	38	40.0
	High School	28	29.5
	University	10	10.5
Work Status	Active	29	30.5
	Retirement	48	50.6
	Housewife	18	18.9
Comorbidity Diseases	Yes	58	61.1
	No	37	38.9
Previous Hospitalisation	Yes	77	81.1
	No	18	18.9
Dialysis Session	Two Times	18	18.9
	Three Times	77	81.1
How Many Years the Disease is Diagnosed	0-1 Year	9	9.5
	2-5 Years	37	38.9
	6-10 Years	29	30.5
	11 Years And Over	20	21.1

Table 2. Comparison of Stress Coping Methods Scale Score with Some Socio Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Socio-demographic Characteristics (n=95)		Stress Coping Methods Scale	Logical Analysis	Positive Evaluation	Seeking Support	Problem Solving Sub-Dimensions
Gender	Female	86.3 ± 4.58	21.33 ± 1.92	23.00 ± 0.01	20.66 ± 1.92	21.33 ± 1.27
	Male	87.50 ± 8.89	22.70 ± 1.41	22.02 ± 3.03	21.16 ± 3.51	21.60 ± 1.78
	p	0.003*	0.001*	0.01*	0.10	0.03*
Marital Status	Married	88.82 ± 8.76	22.88 ± 1.45	23.02 ± 2.44	21.17 ± 3.68	21.73 ± 1.86
	Single	83.21 ± 5.57	20.96 ± 1.42	20.57 ± 2.11	20.64 ± 0.95	21.03 ± 0.83
	p	0.01*	0.17	0.85	0.001*	0.001*
Education Status	Primary Education	90.73 ± 4.61	21.57 ± 1.53	23.52 ± 0.51	23.05 ± 1.02	22.57 ± 1.53
	Middle School	83.50 ± 3.10	21.50 ± 1.52	20.94 ± 1.91	20.02 ± 1.21	21.02 ± 0.71
	High School	93.71 ± 8.46	24.03 ± 0.83	24.14 ± 3.03	23.14 ± 3.03	22.39 ± 1.72
	University	76.00 ± 4.67	22.00 ± 0.01	20.00 ± 0.01	15.00 ± 0.01	19.00 ± 0.01
	P	0.02*	0.01*	0.01*	0.02*	0.01*
Comorbidity Diseases	Yes	88.32 ± 9.33	22.70 ± 1.48	23.03 ± 2.63	21.05 ± 3.95	21.53 ± 1.93
	No	85.35 ± 4.42	21.70 ± 1.80	21.16 ± 2.11	20.97 ± 1.01	21.51 ± 1.12
	P	0.04*	0.006*	0.01*	0.88	0.94
Previous Hospitalisation	Yes	86.97 ± 8.56	22.03 ± 1.74	22.37 ± 2.84	21.02 ± 3.46	21.53 ± 1.69
	No	88.00 ± 4.11	23.50 ± 0.51	22.00 ± 1.02	21.00 ± 1.02	21.50 ± 1.54
	p	0.05*	0.01*	0.02*	0.03*	0.66
Work Status	Active	88.82 ± 4.72	23.00 ± 0.01	22.37 ± 1.26	21.72 ± 1.72	21.71 ± 1.72
	Retirement	87.54 ± 10.11	22.77 ± 1.76	22.00 ± 3.50	20.97 ± 3.96	21.79 ± 1.76
	Housewife	83.50 ± 2.57	20.00 ± 0.01	23.00 ± 0.01	20.00 ± 2.05	20.50 ± 0.51
	p	0.03*	0.01*	0.55	0.06	0.02*

* $p < 0.05$, significant.

Table 3. Stress Coping Methods Scale and Subscale Mean Scores

Scale and Subscales	Min	Max	Mean \pm SD
Stress Coping Methods Scale	76.00	104.00	87.16 \pm 7.90
Logical Analysis	20.00	25.00	22.31 \pm 1.68
Positive Evaluation	18.00	28.00	22.30 \pm 2.60
Seeking Support	15.00	27.00	21.02 \pm 3.14
Problem Solving Sub-Dimensions	19.00	24.00	21.52 \pm 1.65

* $p < 0.05$, significant.

Table 3 shows the mean scores of coping methods with stress scale and sub-dimension scores. Only descriptive statistics are presented. No inferential statistical tests were performed for this table. Accordingly, while the scale score of coping methods with stress was 87.16 ± 7.90 , the sub-dimension scores were 22.31 ± 1.68 for Logical Analysis, 22.30 ± 2.60 for Positive Evaluation, 21.02 ± 3.14 for Seeking Support and 21.52 ± 1.65 for Problem Solving Sub-Dimensions.

Table 4. The Relationship Between Coping with Stress Scale and Liquid Diet Compliance Scales

		Stress Coping Methods Scale
Dialysis Diet Scale	r	0.145
	p	0.16
Fluid Restriction Non-Compliance Scale	r	0.395
	p	0.01*

In Table 4, the relationship between coping with stress and fluid restriction compliance was analyzed using Pearson correlation after confirming normal distribution. The result was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Pearson correlation was applied after confirming normality. Significant correlation was found between fluid restriction compliance and stress coping ($p < 0.05$). Table 4 shows the correlation between the coping with stress scale and the liquid dietary restriction compliance scale. Accordingly, although there was a positive correlation between the two scales, the relationship between coping with stress and fluid restriction compliance was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), while the relationship between dietary restriction and coping with stress was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

There are many factors that may affect liquid diet compliance of haemodialysis patients. These may be socio-demographic characteristics or factors related to the process of adaptation to the disease. In this study, it was determined that gender, marital status, educational status and working style were significantly effective on coping with stress. Sociodemographic characteristics of the patients such as gender, marital status, and educational status affect their coping levels with stress. In

the present study, working status was found to be a significant factor influencing coping with stress among haemodialysis patients. Patients who were actively working demonstrated higher levels of stress coping compared to retired individuals and housewives. This finding may be explained by the positive psychosocial effects of employment, including maintaining social roles, financial independence, daily routines, and a sense of productivity, all of which are known to enhance psychological resilience. Active employment may also promote problem-focused coping strategies by encouraging individuals to remain engaged in social interactions and structured activities. Conversely, unemployment or withdrawal from the workforce may increase feelings of dependency, social isolation, and loss of role identity, thereby weakening stress coping mechanisms. Similar findings in the literature suggest that continued participation in work or productive activities contributes positively to coping capacity and psychological well-being in individuals with chronic diseases, including those undergoing haemodialysis. Given the observed association between stress coping and fluid diet compliance in our study, supporting haemodialysis patients in maintaining appropriate occupational or productive roles may indirectly improve their treatment adherence and overall health outcomes. In particular, male patients were found to have higher levels of coping with

stress than female patients. This may be explained by the fact that men generally develop more active coping strategies¹⁸. Male and married patients were more likely to cope with stress. Considering the positive relationship between coping with stress and liquid diet compliance, it can be said that male and married patients are more compliant. Contrary to the literature, it is thought that women's cooking responsibilities and high workload at home negatively affect the stress level and diet compliance^{10,12}. In addition, the fact that married patients have higher levels of coping with stress than single patients shows that social support and family structure have a positive effect on coping with stress¹⁹.

In our study, in which the level of education and compliance with the disease were evaluated, a similar surprising result was observed. In the studies of^{13,20,21,22}, it was explained that fluid compliance increased as the education level increased. However, in this study, as the level of education increases, the coping with stress scale decreases and liquid diet compliance decreases. This situation can be interpreted as stress increases as information awareness increases and diet compliance is more difficult in working life. Educational level is also an important factor; the fact that university graduates have lower levels of coping with stress suggests that individuals' coping mechanisms may become more complex with increasing educational level. This finding suggests that increased awareness with increasing educational level may negatively affect stress coping methods²³. Another result obtained in our study shows that patients with higher levels of coping with stress also have higher compliance with liquid diet. This result supports that stress management techniques can positively affect patients' health behaviours²⁴. The presence of comorbidity is one of the factors that make liquid diet compliance difficult with stress. It can also be said that people who have not been hospitalised before have stronger coping with stress and therefore liquid diet compliance is better.

Regulation of fluid intake of haemodialysis patients is a critical requirement for the success of treatment processes²¹. While insufficient fluid intake leads to dehydration, excessive fluid intake increases the risk of hypertension and heart failure⁴. Strengthening patients' methods of coping with stress may increase their liquid diet compliance. Psychosocial support may help haemodialysis patients to improve their stress coping skills²⁵. Psychological pressures brought about by the haemodialysis process may negatively affect patients' health

behaviours. Therefore, improving the stress management skills of haemodialysis patients stands out as an important strategy to increase their liquid diet compliance⁶.

This study has some limitations. First of all, the study was conducted in only one hospital, so generalisation of the findings may be limited. In addition, the validity and reliability levels of the scales used in the study may vary in different cultural contexts. It is recommended to conduct similar studies with a larger sample in future studies.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, there is a significant relationship between stress coping levels and liquid diet compliance of haemodialysis patients. The application of stress management techniques may increase the liquid diet compliance of patients and thus support the success of treatment processes. Psychological support of haemodialysis patients may positively affect their health behaviours and this may improve their general health status.

Ethics Committee Approval: Ethics committee approval was received for this study from the ethics committee of *** (Date: 17/05/2023, Sayı: 2023/05-05).

Informed Consent: Informed consent forms were obtained from all patients.

Author Contributions: Concept -FH; Design- FH; Supervision- FH; Resources- FH; Data Collection and/or Processing- FH; Analysis and/or Interpretation- FH; Literature Search- FH; Writing Manuscript- FH; Critical Review- FH; Other- FH

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